

Texture Recognition Methodology Using Convolutional Autoencoders for Mineralogical Liberation Analysis

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Abstract

This study tests a novel unsupervised learning approach using a convolutional autoencoder, named OdysseyNet, for texture recognition in images of mineralogical liberation analysis (MLA). The focus was to extract and analyse textural patterns from MLA images without relying on predefined labels. OdysseyNet was meticulously improved through a phased methodology, starting from basic image reconstructions to complex texture analysis, ultimately producing a series of feature vectors representative of textural patterns. These vectors were analysed through clustering techniques, revealing potential correlations with production metrics. This approach showcases the capability of unsupervised neural networks to provide insightful and unbiased analysis in geoscience, potentially reducing the reliance on costly and time-consuming physical testing.

1 Introduction

Texture analysis in image processing is traditionally aimed at extracting discernible patterns that represent the spatial arrangement and intensity variation within an image. In geological contexts, such as geometallurgy, texture encompasses the sizes, shapes, and distribution of mineral grains, which are crucial to understanding the formation history and functional properties of rocks [36,38]. Traditionally, mineralogical studies have relied on manual observation and pixel counting techniques to estimate mineral quantities from MLA (Mineral Liberation Analysis) images.

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23 However, this approach often fails to capture the complex interrelationships and subtle textural
24 variations present in the rocks.

25 The recognition and classification of textures in digital images is a cornerstone of numerous
26 applications in computer vision, encompassing fields as diverse as medical diagnostics, material
27 science, and geology [9]. At its core, texture represents the spatial distribution and arrangement
28 of pixels within an image, embodying crucial information about the surface characteristics and
29 structural patterns of the depicted objects or materials [3]. In geological contexts, the texture
30 of rocks is influenced by a multitude of factors, including but not limited to, the sizes, shapes,
31 and spatial relationships between mineral grains. These attributes collectively confer a unique
32 identity to rock textures, encapsulating vital insights into geological processes and compositions
33 [5].

34 However, the very diversity that makes textures informatively rich also introduces significant
35 challenges in their automated recognition and classification. The intricate interplay of factors
36 determining the textures of the rock results in a broad spectrum of patterns, each with its nuances
37 and variations [21]. Capturing and interpreting these patterns necessitate computational models
38 capable of understanding complex, high-dimensional data without succumbing to the constraints
39 of predefined labels or categories.

40 Building on the initial efforts in texture recognition, the field has witnessed the emergence
41 of a diverse array of methodologies. These can be broadly categorised into supervised and unsu-
42 pervised techniques, each with its distinct advantages and underlying complexities. Traditional
43 approaches, heavily reliant on manual feature extraction and supervised learning, often fall
44 short in this regard, hampered by the labour-intensive nature of data labelling and the potential
45 biases introduced during the supervision process. In contrast, unsupervised learning methods
46 emerge as a potent alternative, promising to surmount these obstacles by harnessing the inherent
47 structure of the data itself. Free from the need for labelled datasets, unsupervised models can
48 autonomously discover patterns and regularities within images, offering a more objective and
49 comprehensive means of texture analysis. This paradigm shift towards data-driven, unsuper-
50 vised techniques opens up new vistas for texture recognition, especially in domains like geology,
51 where the subtleties and complexities of textures defy simple categorisation. By learning directly
52 from the rich, unlabelled datasets that nature provides, unsupervised neural networks pave the
53 way for more nuanced and adaptive solutions to the perennial challenges of texture recognition.

54 Traditional approaches assume *feature extraction* and *texture classification*. The texture

55 *feature extraction* algorithms could generally be divided into statistics-based, structure-based,
56 model-based, and transformation-based schemes [6]. The statistical methods include histogram-
57 based approaches [14], moment-based algorithms [39], Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrices (GLCM)
58 [1, 18], Binary Gabor Patterns (BGP) [46], Local Binary Patterns (LBP) [33] and energy
59 variation-based approaches [13]. The structural techniques include edge-based methods [27],
60 morphological operators [12] and SIFT descriptors [29]. The model-based techniques include
61 fractal texture models [43], Markov random field texture models [10] and auto-regressive mod-
62 els [31], while the transformation-based schemes include texture-featuring algorithms using 2D
63 Gabor filters [20], 2D wavelet transforms [28], Gabor Wavelets [2] and Curvelet transforms [37].
64 Other feature extraction approaches combine these texture descriptors [45].

65 In the area of supervised learning, traditional techniques like Support Vector Machines
66 (SVMs) [40] and Decision Trees [42] have been employed, leveraging handcrafted features to
67 *classify textures*. These features often include mentioned above Gabor filters [20], which are
68 particularly adept at capturing edge and texture information at various scales and orientations;
69 co-occurrence matrices [1, 18] that quantify the spatial distribution of pixel intensity pairs, thus
70 encapsulating texture regularity; and Local Binary Patterns (LBP) [33], which provide a simple
71 yet efficient method for texture analysis by comparing each pixel with its neighbours. Other
72 supervised machine learning algorithms which are often applied to the *texture classification* in-
73 clude the minimum distance classifier, K-Nearest Neighbour (K-NN), Artificial Neural Networks
74 (ANN) and Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) [7]. However, these supervised methods often re-
75 quire meticulous feature engineering and domain expertise to select or craft features that are
76 most informative for the task at hand. Moreover, their performance can be limited by the
77 inherent variability and complexity of natural textures, which can be difficult to capture with
78 handcrafted features alone.

79 The advent of deep learning has significantly accelerated progress in both supervised and
80 unsupervised texture recognition. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [16], in particular,
81 have become the cornerstone of texture analysis, thanks to their ability to automatically learn
82 hierarchical feature representations from raw images. This shift towards deep learning models,
83 capable of end-to-end learning from large datasets, has not only improved accuracy but also
84 reduced the reliance on domain-specific knowledge for feature selection. However, despite the
85 success of supervised deep learning models, the reliance on large, annotated datasets presents a
86 notable limitation, particularly in domains where labelled data are scarce or expensive to obtain.

87 In this context, unsupervised neural networks, and graph-based clustering methods, which do
88 not require labelled data for training, have emerged as a promising alternative.

89 Unsupervised learning approaches seek to alleviate some of these challenges by discovering
90 patterns and structures within the data without the need for labelled examples. Techniques such
91 as k-means clustering and its variations [4,15,35] and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [22]
92 have been applied to group similar textures and reduce dimensionality, respectively. More
93 advanced methods like autoencoders, particularly Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) [23], and
94 Self-Organizing Maps (SOMs) [24,25] further push the boundaries by enabling more nuanced
95 feature extraction and data representation. These methods have the advantage of learning
96 directly from the data, potentially uncovering intricate patterns that may not be readily apparent
97 or easily encoded with handcrafted features [34,44,47].

98 Each of these approaches, from the simplest clustering techniques to complex deep learning
99 architectures, contributes uniquely to the rich tapestry of methods available for texture recog-
100 nition. They illustrate the evolving landscape of the field, where the choice of method is often
101 dictated by the specific requirements of the application, the nature of the data, and the avail-
102 ability of computational resources. The next chapter will explain in more details why among
103 all the available feature extraction and classification methods, SOMs and Autoencoders were
104 employed for the current work.

105 Self-Organizing Maps, a type of unsupervised neural network, offer a unique approach to
106 texture analysis by projecting high-dimensional data onto a lower-dimensional space while pre-
107 serving the topological relationships between data points. This capability allows SOMs to cluster
108 and visualise texture patterns, facilitating the interpretation and classification of complex tex-
109 tures. Studies such as Kohonen et al. [25] have demonstrated the effectiveness of SOMs in
110 grouping similar texture patterns, underscoring their applicability in various image analysis
111 tasks.

112 Recent studies highlight SOMs' utility in grouping similar texture patterns by projecting
113 high-dimensional data onto a lower-dimensional space, thereby preserving topological relation-
114 ships between data points. This feature of SOMs is instrumental in clustering and visualising
115 texture patterns, facilitating complex texture classification and interpretation. For instance,
116 a novel unsupervised texture classification technique incorporating anisotropic diffusion-based
117 multi-scale analysis and weight-connected graph clustering demonstrates the effectiveness of
118 unsupervised approaches in recognising and classifying textures without pre-known class num-

119 bers, emphasising their flexibility and adaptability in handling texture data [6]. Another study
120 presents a comparative analysis of clustering quality in SOMs, particularly in the context of hu-
121 man posture classification, underscoring SOMs' capacity to recognise postures without relying
122 on manually labelled data. This work introduces a new clustering quality score, the discriminant
123 score (DS), to select the most appropriate number of clusters, which corresponds to the number
124 of postures. This method emphasises the strength of unsupervised learning in eliminating sub-
125 jective bias and reducing the manual effort in labelling, especially in tasks where data variability
126 and high dimensionality are significant challenges [11].

127 These few examples from recent literature underscore the growing significance of unsuper-
128 vised neural networks, like SOMs, in texture feature analysis and clustering. By leveraging the
129 intrinsic structures within data, SOMs provide a robust framework for analysing complex tex-
130 tures without the constraints of labelled datasets, marking a promising direction in unsupervised
131 learning applications.

132 Autoencoders, another class of unsupervised neural networks [17], have gained attention
133 for their ability to learn compressed representations of data through an encoder-decoder archi-
134 tecture. By reconstructing the input from a lower-dimensional latent space, autoencoders can
135 capture salient features of textures, making them suitable for tasks such as texture classification
136 and segmentation. The work by Hinton et al. [19] highlights the potential of deep autoencoders
137 in learning efficient representations of data, including textured images.

138 Autoencoders, with their unique encoder-decoder structure, offer a powerful framework for
139 unsupervised learning [26], especially in the realm of texture recognition and analysis. These
140 neural networks excel in distilling high-dimensional data into a more manageable latent space,
141 capturing essential texture characteristics vital for classification, segmentation, and even gener-
142 ation of textures.

143 The transformative capability of autoencoders is showcased in their application to feature ex-
144 traction and dimensionality reduction tasks, where they discern pertinent features from textures
145 without the need for labelled data. A noteworthy application involves leveraging Variational
146 Autoencoders (VAEs) for generating new textures by learning from a dataset of existing ones,
147 indicating their potential not just in recognition but also in creative generation of textured
148 patterns [23].

149 In the context of segmentation, Convolutional Autoencoders (CAEs) [32] have demonstrated
150 significant success. By learning to compress and then reconstruct input images, CAEs can

151 identify texture boundaries and features with high precision, which was particularly useful in
152 medical imaging where texture details can indicate different tissue types or pathological condi-
153 tions. Research by Makhzani et al. [30] emphasises the efficacy of Adversarial Autoencoders in
154 learning robust latent representations that can be used for unsupervised clustering of complex
155 data, including textures, showcasing the versatility of autoencoders in various texture analysis
156 applications.

157 Further extending the utility of autoencoders, studies have applied them in cross-domain
158 texture recognition tasks, where the challenge is to recognise textures under varying conditions
159 and from different domains. The adaptability of autoencoders to handle such variations without
160 explicit labelling demonstrates their substantial advantage in unsupervised learning scenarios
161 where acquiring labelled data is impractical or impossible. Together, these several examples
162 underline the expanding role of autoencoders in texture analysis. By learning to compress and
163 reconstruct textures, autoencoders not only facilitate recognition and segmentation but also
164 pave the way for novel applications such as texture synthesis and cross-domain recognition,
165 emphasising their importance in advancing unsupervised learning techniques for texture-related
166 tasks.

167 The integration of unsupervised neural networks into texture recognition systems offers a
168 path forward in addressing the challenges associated with traditional methods. By leveraging the
169 ability of these networks to learn from unlabelled data, researchers and practitioners can develop
170 more robust and adaptable models for analysing complex texture patterns in 2D images. As this
171 field continues to evolve, it is imperative to explore innovative neural network architectures and
172 training strategies that can further enhance the capability of unsupervised models in texture
173 recognition. The integration of unsupervised learning with semi-supervised and transfer learning
174 approaches represents an exciting avenue for future research, promising to unlock new potentials
175 in the automated analysis of textured images.

176 In our investigation into texture recognition within 2D MLA images, the authors confronted
177 the challenge of analysing rock particles characterised by intricate structures and a diverse
178 mineral composition. Given the complexity of these datasets, it became imperative to employ
179 a method that was not only robust but also adaptable to the wide array of textures present.
180 Convolutional Autoencoders (CAEs) emerged as the method of choice due to their proficiency
181 in handling high-dimensional data and their capability to learn efficient data representations
182 directly from the images, without reliance on pre-defined labels or manual feature extraction.

183 The decision to utilise Convolutional Autoencoders was underpinned by several considera-
184 tions. Firstly, the encoder-decoder architecture inherent to autoencoders facilitates the learning
185 of compressed data representations, capturing essential texture features crucial for effective clas-
186 sification and segmentation tasks. This attribute is particularly valuable when dealing with com-
187 plex textures where the spatial relationships and properties of mineral grains vary significantly.
188 Secondly, the convolutional layers within CAEs are adept at preserving spatial hierarchies be-
189 tween textures, enabling the model to adaptively discern and classify intricate patterns in the
190 data. Lastly, the unsupervised nature of autoencoders ensures that the learning process is free
191 from biases that might arise from pre-labelled data, allowing the model to uncover natural
192 groupings and patterns within the textures based on the data itself.

193 Through the employment of Convolutional Autoencoders, our work endeavours to advance
194 the methodology of texture recognition by leveraging deep learning's capacity for unsupervised
195 learning. By doing so, we aim to illustrate the potential of these models to autonomously
196 navigate the complex landscape of 2D MLA images, recognising and classifying textures based
197 solely on the inherent characteristics of the data. This approach not only enhances the accuracy
198 and reliability of texture analysis but also broadens the scope of applications in geosciences,
199 including geometallurgy where understanding the nuanced details of textures is paramount to
200 analyse and predict production properties.

201 The advantage of our approach lies in its ability to integrate multiple textural indicators -
202 ranging from mineral morphology to the spatial relationships among different minerals - into
203 a coherent analytical framework. This is achieved through the network's capability to encode
204 significant textural information into a compact, interpretable form within the bottleneck layer
205 of the autoencoder. The network is trained to reconstruct the input images from this encoded
206 representation, ensuring that the essential textural features are preserved and can be used for
207 further analysis. By moving beyond mere pixel counting to a more holistic analysis of textures,
208 our methodology offers significant advantages for predicting the productivity potential of rock
209 samples. This can lead to more efficient resource utilisation in mining operations, as predictive
210 models based on texture analysis can potentially reduce the need for extensive laboratory sample
211 testing.

212 In conclusion, the use of convolutional autoencoders in our study is a testament to the
213 evolving capabilities of neural networks in the field of texture recognition. By focusing on an
214 unsupervised and adaptive methodology, we aspire to underscore the significance of deep learning

215 techniques in deciphering the rich tapestry of textures present in MLA images, thereby contribut-
216 ing to the broader understanding and application of texture analysis in geoscience research. The
217 findings of this research could significantly enhance our understanding of mineralogical textures,
218 improving predictive models in geoscience.

219 **2 Methodology**

220 **2.1 Motivation**

221 The intricate task of texture recognition in our study stems from two primary challenges: the
222 complex textural patterns present in the rock samples and the absence of predefined labels for
223 these textures. Traditional methods that rely on handcrafted features or supervised learning
224 often falter in such settings where the textural patterns are diverse, and no ground truth is
225 available for guidance.

226 Our objective was to test a methodology that allows the neural network to independently
227 discover and learn these textural patterns from the data itself, akin to how a chess player
228 discerns patterns on a chessboard [8]. This approach is especially pertinent in situations where
229 the textural components - such as grain size, shape, and spatial distribution - are not only varied
230 but also carry significant geological information.

231 Given these conditions, we opted for an unsupervised learning approach using autoencoders,
232 specifically convolutional autoencoders. The choice of convolutional autoencoders was driven by
233 their capacity to handle multiple levels of abstraction and complexity in image data, which is
234 crucial for accurately capturing and reconstructing the hierarchical features of mineral textures.
235 The encoder-decoder structure of autoencoders facilitates a deep learning-based, self-taught
236 mechanism where the network learns to compress (encode) the input into a dense representation
237 and subsequently reconstruct (decode) the output to match the input as closely as possible and
238 reasonable.

239 The key component of our model is the bottleneck layer, situated between the encoder and
240 the decoder, which serves as a compact representation of the input textures. The effectiveness
241 of this representation is evaluated based on the accuracy of the reconstruction, implying that
242 a faithful reconstruction from this compressed representation confirms the network's ability to
243 identify and encode relevant textural features.

244 By training the network to minimise the difference between the original images and their

245 reconstructions, we can infer that the learned representations in the bottleneck layer effectively
246 capture the essential characteristics of different rock textures. This methodology not only ad-
247 dresses the absence of labelled data but also reduces the potential bias introduced by supervised
248 methods, allowing for a more authentic and unbiased exploration of textural patterns.

249 As will be demonstrated below, our methodology for texture recognition in MLA images
250 employs a balanced strategy that bears resemblance to the principles of denoising autoencoders.
251 Denoising autoencoders are a type of neural network designed to enhance the robustness of
252 learned representations by training the model to reconstruct the original input from a corrupted
253 version. This approach helps the network focus on the most significant features of the data,
254 effectively learning to ignore noise and irrelevant details [16,41].

255 In our study, we introduced a pre-processing step where the primary mineral phase in each
256 image was highlighted, while all other minerals were masked with white. This pre-processing
257 creates a simplified input that emphasises the main mineral content, akin to the noisy inputs
258 used in denoising autoencoders. The autoencoder is then tasked with reconstructing the detailed
259 original image from this simplified version, thereby learning to recognise and restore intricate
260 textural patterns from minimal cues.

261 This strategy aligns with the denoising autoencoder’s goal of learning meaningful and robust
262 features from incomplete or corrupted data. By presenting the network with these pre-processed
263 images, we aimed to enhance its ability to identify and encode the underlying textural charac-
264 teristics that are crucial for accurate texture recognition and classification.

265 The effectiveness of this approach is demonstrated by the network’s ability to accurately
266 reconstruct images and capture the essential features necessary for subsequent analysis. This
267 methodology not only validates the use of autoencoders for texture analysis but also highlights
268 the potential of using our techniques to improve the robustness and accuracy of texture recog-
269 nition models in geoscience applications.

270 **2.2 Dataset**

271 The dataset consists of MLA images from Olympic Dam ore samples. Due to proprietary
272 constraints, specific geological context and sample origins cannot be disclosed. However, the
273 diversity of 60 minerals across varied rock types ensures representative textural patterns for
274 method development.

275 Our study utilised Mineral Liberation Analysis 2D images, which are high-resolution scans of

276 rock particles embedded within an epoxy matrix. MLA is a specialised imaging technique used
 277 in mineralogy to quantify mineral grain size distributions and associations within rock samples.
 278 This technology generates multi-spectral images where each pixel colour - represented through
 279 red, green, and blue (RGB) values - corresponds to different minerals.

280 The dataset comprised several thousand MLA images, each depicting various mineral grains
 281 embedded within rock particles. The diversity of the dataset was significant, with a total of
 282 60 distinct minerals identified (Figure 1), varying widely in abundance and spatial distribution.
 283 Not all minerals appeared in every image, reflecting the natural variability in rock compositions.

284 For consistency and to manage computational resources effectively, we standardised the
 285 images to a uniform size of 5120×5120 pixels (Figure 2a and 2b). This preprocessing step
 286 ensured that each image, regardless of its original size, was adjusted to a standard scale without
 287 altering the inherent textural and compositional information.

Figure 1: Mineral list with MLA false colours (total 60 minerals).

288 Approximately 2500 particles were selected for detailed analysis. The selection criteria were
 289 based solely on image quality and coverage, ensuring a representative sample of the overall

290 (a) An example of the input MLA image: original
291 size (7163 by 9135 pixels).

292 (b) An example of the input MLA image: standardised
293 size (5120 by 5120 pixels).

Figure 2: Examples of MLA images before and after standardisation.

290 diversity in mineral textures. Importantly, no additional geological or mineralogical data were
291 used to influence the selection process. This approach was adopted to maintain an unbiased
292 perspective in the subsequent unsupervised learning analysis, focusing purely on the data-derived
293 features without preconceived notions about the geological context.

294 **2.3 Execution (Compiling the network)**

295 Our research project was fundamentally an exploratory venture aimed at uncovering unknown
296 patterns within MLA images of rock particles. Given the complexity of the task and the absence
297 of predetermined outcomes or ground truth, building of a clear, transparent, and reproducible
298 workflow was paramount. This approach was designed not only to facilitate our understanding of
299 complex mineral textures but also to suggest a versatile tool that could be adapted and utilised
300 for a broad range of geoscientific applications without being confined to specific rock types or
301 geographical conditions.

302 To navigate the challenges of unsupervised learning in a Research and Development con-
303 text, our methodology was carefully segmented into three progressive phases. This structured
304 approach ensured that each phase could be independently verified and optimised, providing a
305 solid foundation for the subsequent steps:

- 306 1. **Data preparation:** The primary focus was on ensuring uniformity across all input data
307 and preparing the data to train the network properly. We processed several thousand MLA
308 images, standardising them to a consistent size of 5120×5120 pixels and converted them
309 into binary data as will be explained further. This standardisation was crucial to ensure
310 that the subsequent modelling phases could operate under consistent input conditions.
- 311 2. **Architecture building and whole image testing:** In this phase, we iteratively build
312 and refined our convolutional autoencoder architecture. Initial testing on whole images
313 allowed us to adjust the model to effectively handle and reconstruct large-scale textural
314 variations, setting the stage for more detailed analyses.
- 315 3. **Particle isolation and analysis of individual particles:** The final phase concentrated
316 on the detailed textures within individual rock particles. By focusing on these elements,
317 we were able to fine-tune the model's accuracy in texture classification and reconstruction,
318 providing deeper insights into the mineralogical composition of the samples.

319 This phased experimental approach was essential for several reasons. Firstly, it allowed
320 us to methodically enhance the model's capability with each step, ensuring that each layer of
321 texture complexity was adequately captured and represented. Secondly, it provided a clear and
322 logical progression for the research, crucial for maintaining transparency and reproducibility in a
323 project where the outcomes were not predefined. Lastly, by validating the model's performance
324 at each stage, we could confidently assert that the bottleneck layer - our model's critical feature
325 - accurately encapsulated the essential characteristics of the mineral textures.

326 By employing this methodical experimental design, we established a robust framework for
327 evaluating and utilising unsupervised learning techniques in a domain traditionally dominated
328 by more biased supervised methods. This approach not only aligns with the scientific rigour
329 required for R&D but also enhances the adaptability and applicability of our findings across
330 different sectors within the field of geoscience.

331 **2.3.1 Data Preparation: image conversion and grouping**

332 In the initial phase of our workflow, extensive preprocessing was crucial to adapt the input data
333 for effective neural network training. This involved two main steps: resizing the images for
334 uniformity and transforming them into a format more conducive for unsupervised learning.

335 To ensure consistency across all samples, each MLA image was cut to a standardised dimen-
336 sion of 5120×5120 pixels. This uniformity is vital for neural networks, which often require fixed
337 input sizes and benefit from standardised data formats to perform optimally.

338 Beyond resizing, the images underwent a significant transformation to highlight the textural
339 features relevant for our study. Each of the 60 minerals identified in the samples was grouped into
340 one of five broad mineral groups (Table 1). This grouping was based on shared characteristics
341 or geological significance, which simplifies the model’s task by reducing the complexity of the
342 input data. Five mineral groups were used: hematite, non-hematite gangue, quartz, sericite, and
343 sulphides. The workflow allows utilising different grouping schemes depending on the purpose
344 of texture recognition. For example, if it is required to focus on copper-rich minerals, those
345 minerals should be grouped together and separated from other sulphides.

346 Subsequently, the RGB images were converted into binary 5-channel images, where each
347 channel represented one of the five mineral groups. In these binary images, a pixel value of 1
348 (white) indicated the presence of a mineral from the corresponding group, while a value of 0
349 (black) represented either the background or other minerals not belonging to that group. This
350 binary encoding reduces the variability within the input data, making patterns more distinct
351 and easier for the network to learn.

352 Binary encoding simplifies the input data by reducing the range of pixel values. In the context
353 of unsupervised learning, where the goal is to capture inherent patterns without prior labels,
354 binary encoding helps to highlight essential features by eliminating less relevant variations.
355 This is particularly beneficial for convolutional autoencoders, which excel at capturing spatial
356 hierarchies and patterns in image data. By focusing on stark contrasts between mineral groups
357 and the background, the network can more effectively learn to differentiate and reconstruct
358 complex textural patterns inherent in the geological samples.

359 The conversion process not only tailored the images to the specific needs of our convolu-
360 tional autoencoder but also aligned with our objective to develop an unbiased methodological
361 framework capable of independently recognising textural patterns. This step was instrumental
362 in setting a solid foundation for the subsequent phases of the model’s training and evaluation.

363 **2.3.2 Architecture Evolution: working with the whole images**

364 Following data preparation, the next crucial phase involved the systematic building and refine-
365 ment of the convolutional autoencoder architecture, tailored specifically for handling complex

Table 1: Minerals divided into five groups for further processing.

Channel 0 (hematite)	Channel 1 (non-hematite gangue)	Channel 2 (quartz)	Channel 3 (sericite)	Channel 4 (sulfide)
FeO	Brannerite Coffinite Thorite Uraninite Uraninite_Cu_Pb Uraninite_Pb_REE Uranothorite Bastnasite Crandellite_Grp Florencite Synchysite Monazite Ilmenorutile Rutile Ilmenite Albite Al_Hydroxide Anhydrite Ankerite Apatite Barite Barite_Sr Chlorite_1 Chlorite_2 Chlorite_3 Corundum Dolomite Fluorite Kaolinite Orthoclase Schorl Sellaite Siderite Siderite_Mn Topaz Xenotime Zircon	Quartz	Sericite	Bornite Carrolite Chalcocite Chalcopyrite Covellite Domeykite Native_Copper Tennantite Altaite Clausthalite Galena Sphalerite Molybdenite Bismuthinite Tellurobismuthite Cobaltite Lollingite Pyrite Pyrrhotite Safflorite

366 textural patterns. Given the dual nature of mineral distribution - ranging from abundant min-
367 erals like hematite, quartz, and sericite to sparser groups such as non-hematite gangue and
368 sulphides - our approach entailed separate network configurations for each group. This differen-
369 tiation was pivotal in addressing the unique challenges posed by each mineral's frequency and
370 distribution.

371 Initially, we converted the coloured MLA images into binary 5-channel images (Figure 3),
372 where each channel corresponded to one of the five mineral groups, transformed into binary
373 format to enhance the neural network's focus on texture-specific features. The construction of
374 the network started from the simple configuration with three hidden layers and 8 filters for the
375 first layer. The architecture's complexity was progressively increased, from simpler models to
376 more sophisticated ones, to determine the optimal configuration in terms of layer depth, filter
377 size, number of filters, activation functions, dropout rates etc. This gradual escalation allowed
378 us to pinpoint the most effective structure for texture recognition and reconstruction. The final
379 configuration which demonstrated the best balance between the complexity of the model and
380 the accuracy of the results was finally built through iterative experiments.

Figure 3: Binary 5-channel images.

381 To validate the network's performance, a series of tests were conducted comparing the neural
382 network's output with traditional downscale-upscale algorithms. This not only assessed the
383 network's accuracy in reconstructing textures but also provided insights into the learning depth,
384 particularly how well the network could recognise and predict intricate textural details without
385 merely duplicating visible features. Visual inspections played a crucial role during this phase.
386 Anomalies such as irregular shapes or unexpected textural elements in the output were carefully
387 analysed. Such artifacts, rather than being viewed as errors, were interpreted as indicators
388 of the network's capability to learn, and generalise textural patterns beyond simple copying,
389 suggesting a deeper, more abstract understanding of the data (Figure 4 and 5).

390 The network was rigorously trained using a dataset of 1050 images, split into 80% for training

Figure 4: A comparison of original (input), reconstructed (by the autoencoder) images and the image obtained by downscaling-upscaling process for three "abundant channels" (from left to right: hematite, quartz, sericite).

391 and 20% for validation purposes. To further test the robustness and generalisability of our
 392 models, 1324 unseen images were employed. Notably, the network designed for sparse minerals
 393 was configured to be deeper than that for abundant minerals, reflecting the increased complexity
 394 needed to capture less frequent textural patterns. In our pursuit to enhance the accuracy of
 395 reconstructing sparse minerals in our dataset, we also experimented with assigning differential
 396 weights to various mineral groups. This approach was intended to accentuate the less abundant
 397 mineral groups during the training process of our convolutional autoencoders. Initially, we
 398 hypothesised that by adjusting the network's focus towards these sparse minerals, it would yield
 399 a more balanced and detailed reconstruction across all mineral types.

400 However, the results of this experiment were mixed. When implemented across all five
 401 mineral groups within the "abundant" network framework, this strategy did not significantly
 402 improve the model's performance. This outcome could likely be attributed to the overwhelming
 403 presence of more abundant minerals, which may have diluted the effect of the weighted empha-
 404 sis on the sparse groups. Conversely, when we applied similar weighted strategies within the
 405 confines of the "sparse" mineral groups alone, the results were markedly better. This tailored

Figure 5: A comparison of original (input), reconstructed (by the autoencoder) images and the image obtained by downscaling-upscaling process for two "sparse channels" (from left to right: non-hematite gangue, sulphides).

406 approach within a more controlled group setting allowed the network to effectively learn and
 407 emphasise the nuances of less prevalent minerals without being overshadowed by the dominant
 408 groups. This experiment underscored the complexity of our dataset and the challenges associ-
 409 ated with balancing the representation of highly varied mineral abundance. It also highlighted
 410 the potential of adaptive learning strategies in managing such imbalances, particularly when
 411 applied judiciously within specific subsets of the data.

412 After finishing this part of work, we further refined our methodology by processing the
 413 MLA images in smaller patches of 512×512 pixels. This "patch" approach was crucial for
 414 focusing on finer textural details, which is a precursor to the next step - analysing individual
 415 rock particles. By processing these patches, we aimed to assess the network's capability to
 416 accurately reconstruct and analyse detailed patterns within a more confined spatial context
 417 (Figure 6 and 7).

Figure 6: A comparison of original (input), reconstructed (by the autoencoder) images and the image obtained by downscaling-upscaling process for three "abundant channels" (from left to right: hematite, quartz, sericite). An example of image patches.

418 This patch-based method also served as a testbed to confirm the effectiveness of our network
 419 configuration before applying it to isolated particles. The workflow for handling these image
 420 patches mirrored that of the whole images, maintaining consistency in the network architecture

Figure 7: A comparison of original (input), reconstructed (by the autoencoder) images and the image obtained by downscaling-upscaling process for two "sparse channels" (from left to right: non-hematite gangue, sulphides). An example of image patches.

421 and parameters. Encouragingly, the results demonstrated that the same network configuration
422 adeptly handled the patches, effectively reconstructing the detailed textures without the need
423 for additional complexity in the network architecture. This outcome was promising, affirming
424 our model’s capacity to discern and learn intricate textural nuances, thereby setting a solid
425 foundation for the analysis of the isolated particles.

426 **2.3.3 Particle isolation: analysis of individual particles**

427 Having established a robust network architecture capable of recognising and reconstructing tex-
428 tural patterns from binary images, we proceeded to the third and final phase of our methodology
429 workflow. This phase aimed to evaluate the network’s ability to discern not only the morpholog-
430 ical features of mineral grains but also the complex interrelationships between different mineral
431 types.

432 Previously, we built and tested our networks on the whole images and patches of those
433 images. This approach helped reduce the training time and understand whether the network
434 could effectively learn grain shapes and other morphological features. However, this approach
435 was not suitable to be utilised for MLA data analysis due to the fact that the distribution of
436 the rock particles on the analysed MLA images was random, so, it does not present any useful
437 textural information. Proper textural analysis required to work on the particles themselves
438 ignoring the texture of the whole MLA images. To focus only on the rock particle textural
439 features, we isolated individual rock particles from the MLA images, placing each within a
440 uniform 800×800 pixel pad. This size was strategically chosen to accommodate the variance
441 in grain sizes without distorting the larger grains, while still maintaining discernible detail in
442 smaller grains. In this phase, alongside the binary images, we incorporated the original colour
443 images and a set of ”pre-processed” images. The pre-processed images highlighted the primary
444 mineral phase of each particle against a white background (in addition to a black background
445 which marked the area outside of the rock particle), effectively isolating it from other minerals
446 (Figure 8). This approach was utilised to test the network’s ability to reconstruct the textural
447 context and mineral association knowing primarily the dominant mineral.

448 Leveraging a simplified version of the abundant minerals’ network architecture, we incre-
449 mentally introduced complexity to assess the network’s performance in a controlled manner.
450 We started training the network from 320 particles, then moved to 2,790 particles and finally
451 to 5,644 particles. When the network demonstrated the accurate reconstruction of the coloured

Figure 8: Isolated particles input images (binary 5-channel images are summed together). Three random rock particles of different size were chosen for visualisation to demonstrated that the textural feature might be of different scale.

452 images, we started training the developed network on a larger dataset. That dataset included 54
453 MLA images (26,623 isolated particles). Another experimental training set included 100 images,
454 translated into 50,954 particles, representing a diverse array of rock types to ensure a compre-
455 hensive learning scope. However, the accuracy of the 100-image and 54-image models was quite
456 comparable, so finally the network trained on the 54 images was chosen for further work while
457 the 100-image network will be kept as a backup. In the future, if it is required to retrain the
458 model with more than five mineral groups, it will be done using the 54-image dataset. The built
459 architecture is presented in Table 2. For a stringent test of its practical applicability, the network
460 was finally evaluated using an independent set of 56 images (76,101 particles), which were not
461 included in the training or validation sets. This step was crucial in affirmatively determining the
462 efficacy of the network in real world scenarios. Those images were used to estimate how accurate
463 the trained network can reconstruct the unseen images. Also, that set of images was used to
464 extract the feature vectors as will be discussed in the next chapter (Results and Discussion).

465 To sum all, this detailed, phased execution workflow not only solidified the foundational
466 understanding of the convolutional autoencoder’s capabilities for the explored dataset but also
467 confirmed its effectiveness in recognising and interpreting complex mineral textures. The sub-
468 sequent chapter will delve into the results and discussions, presenting a comprehensive analysis
469 of the network’s performance and the insights gleaned from these experiments.

470 **3 Results and Discussion**

471 In our study, we tested a convolutional autoencoder tailored for texture recognition in mineralog-
472 ical analyses, focusing on the detailed textural features present in rock particles on MLA images.
473 The architecture of this autoencoder consists of an encoder and a decoder segment, designed to
474 compress, and subsequently reconstruct the image data, capturing the intricate textural details
475 effectively.

476 In this exploration of geological textures through machine learning, our main computational
477 tool was aptly named OdysseyNet, reflecting not only its training on data from the Olympic
478 Dam but also the long and intricate journey of research and discovery unsupervised learning
479 embodies. Much like Homer’s Odyssey, this unsupervised approach embarked on a complex
480 voyage through uncharted territories of data, striving to uncover hidden patterns and insights
481 within the mineralogical landscapes of rock images.

Table 2: Developed network model.

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Parameters #	Connected to
Input_Binary (InputLayer)	(None, 800, 800, 5)	0	
Input_Preprocessed (InputLayer)	(None, 800, 800, 3)	0	
concatenate (Concatenate)	(None, 800, 800, 8)	0	Input_Binary[0][0] Input_Preprocessed[0][0]
conv2d (Conv2D)	(None, 800, 800, 32)	2336	concatenate[0][0]
batch_normalization (BatchNormalization)	(None, 800, 800, 32)	128	conv2d[0][0]
activation (Activation)	(None, 800, 800, 32)	0	batch_normalization[0][0]
max_pooling2d (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 400, 400, 32)	0	activation[0][0]
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)	(None, 400, 400, 64)	18496	max_pooling2d[0][0]
batch_normalization_1 (BatchNormalization)	(None, 400, 400, 64)	256	conv2d_1[0][0]
activation_1 (Activation)	(None, 400, 400, 64)	0	batch_normalization_1[0][0]
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 200, 200, 64)	0	activation_1[0][0]
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)	(None, 200, 200, 128)	73856	max_pooling2d_1[0][0]
batch_normalization_2 (BatchNormalization)	(None, 200, 200, 128)	512	conv2d_2[0][0]
activation_2 (Activation)	(None, 200, 200, 128)	0	batch_normalization_2[0][0]
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 100, 100, 128)	0	activation_2[0][0]
conv2d_3 (Conv2D)	(None, 100, 100, 256)	295168	max_pooling2d_2[0][0]
batch_normalization_3 (BatchNormalization)	(None, 100, 100, 256)	1024	conv2d_3[0][0]
activation_3 (Activation)	(None, 100, 100, 256)	0	batch_normalization_3[0][0]
max_pooling2d_3 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 50, 50, 256)	0	activation_3[0][0]
conv2d_4 (Conv2D)	(None, 50, 50, 512)	1180160	max_pooling2d_3[0][0]
batch_normalization_4 (BatchNormalization)	(None, 50, 50, 512)	2048	conv2d_4[0][0]
conv2d_transpose (Conv2DTranspose)	(None, 100, 100, 256)	1179904	batch_normalization_4[0][0]
batch_normalization_5 (BatchNormalization)	(None, 100, 100, 256)	1024	conv2d_transpose[0][0]
activation_4 (Activation)	(None, 100, 100, 256)	0	batch_normalization_5[0][0]
conv2d_transpose_1 (Conv2DTranspose)	(None, 200, 200, 128)	295040	activation_4[0][0]
batch_normalization_6 (BatchNormalization)	(None, 200, 200, 128)	512	conv2d_transpose_1[0][0]
activation_5 (Activation)	(None, 200, 200, 128)	0	batch_normalization_6[0][0]
conv2d_transpose_2 (Conv2DTranspose)	(None, 400, 400, 64)	73792	activation_5[0][0]
batch_normalization_7 (BatchNormalization)	(None, 400, 400, 64)	256	conv2d_transpose_2[0][0]
activation_6 (Activation)	(None, 400, 400, 64)	0	batch_normalization_7[0][0]
conv2d_transpose_3 (Conv2DTranspose)	(None, 800, 800, 32)	18464	activation_6[0][0]
batch_normalization_8 (BatchNormalization)	(None, 800, 800, 32)	128	conv2d_transpose_3[0][0]
activation_7 (Activation)	(None, 800, 800, 32)	0	batch_normalization_8[0][0]
Output (Conv2D)	(None, 800, 800, 3)	867	activation_7[0][0]
Total params: 3,143,911			
Trainable params: 3,141,863			
Non-trainable params: 2,048			

482 Training OdysseyNet represents the culmination of our efforts to test a novel, unsupervised
483 approach to texture analysis in the field of geosciences. By leveraging the inherent data-driven
484 capabilities of convolutional autoencoders and integrating them with sophisticated clustering
485 techniques, we've implemented a methodology that not only enhances the understanding of
486 mineral textures but also paves the way for innovative applications in geometallurgy.

487 Our model's architecture integrates dual input streams, accommodating binary images di-
488 vided into several channels - each representing a different mineral group - and pre-processed
489 images that emphasise the primary mineral phase. The encoder part comprises multiple convo-
490 lutional layers paired with batch normalisation and ReLU activation, ensuring non-linear pro-
491 cessing of input data. MaxPooling layers interspersed between convolutional layers help reduce
492 spatial dimensions, isolating essential features while retaining crucial textural information.

493 At the centre of the encoder is the bottleneck layer, equipped with 512 filters (Figure 2)
494 designed to condense the image data into a dense, informative feature vector. This compact
495 representation is presumed to encapsulate all vital textural information necessary for accurate
496 image reconstruction by the decoder.

497 The decoder mirrors the encoder in complexity, utilising Convolutional Transpose layers to
498 gradually upscale the condensed feature vector back to its original dimensionality. The process
499 culminates in an output layer that generates the final reconstructed image, aiming to match the
500 input image's textural attributes as closely as possible and reasonable.

501 The principle underlying the above convolutional autoencoder is predicated on the assump-
502 tion that accurate image reconstruction by the autoencoder indicates a successful capture of
503 essential textural features in the bottleneck layer. If the autoencoder effectively and accurately
504 reconstructs the input images - a claim substantiated by the rigorous methodology - the output
505 from the bottleneck can serve as a distinctive feature vector or signature for each image.

506 In the absence of ground truth data and given the exploratory nature of the study, the
507 evaluation of OdysseyNet's reconstruction performance necessitated innovative approaches. The
508 primary objective of the autoencoder was not to replicate the minute details of the mineral
509 grains but to capture and analyse the overarching textural patterns which could be correlated
510 with production metrics. To this end, a qualitative assessment strategy was adopted, focusing
511 on visual analysis of the reconstructed images.

512 The accuracy of the reconstructions was assessed through analysis of quantitative metrics
513 and careful visual examination, with specific attention to key aspects such as grain size, shape,

514 and mineral content. Quantitative metrics computed during training showed progressive im-
 515 provement as the network architecture evolved. Initial experiments on whole images yielded
 516 moderate results (validation MAE 0.043-0.129, PSNR 13.4-18.3 dB, SSIM loss 0.21-0.49),
 517 which improved substantially when processing image patches (SSIM loss improved to 0.14-0.04,
 518 MAE 0.059-0.154, PSNR 14.0-20.6 dB). The final model for isolated particles achieved ex-
 519 cellent reconstruction quality with very low mean absolute error (validation MAE 0.003 and
 520 edge loss 0.008), representing a 40-fold improvement over initial whole-image models. Visual
 521 examination confirmed that while the exact contours and minutest details of grain shapes were
 522 not perfectly reconstructed, the aspect ratio - a critical shape descriptor - was generally well-
 523 preserved. (Figure 9). This preservation of aspect ratio is particularly significant in the context
 524 of textural analysis, where the relative dimensions of features can impart important geological
 525 information. In terms of mineral content, the reconstructions occasionally exhibited errors such
 526 as the misidentification of minerals within the same group, for instance, pyrite being mistaken
 527 for safflorite (Figure 10). However, these inaccuracies were limited and only happened within the
 528 same mineral groups, so that, they did not detract from the overall utility of the reconstructed
 529 outputs for textural pattern analysis.

Figure 9: Comparison of input and reconstructed images. The figure shows that some small mineral grain details may disappear, but the overall reconstruction is remarkably accurate.

530 As it was mentioned before, we hypothesise that the feature vectors may correlate with
 531 known production metrics for each image, offering a predictive insight into the rock sample's
 532 productivity without further empirical testing. By applying the trained model to 56 additional
 533 unseen images and extracting 76,101 feature vectors, we evaluate this hypothesis, aiming to

Figure 10: Comparison of input and reconstructed images. The figure shows that some mineral grains may be mistaken, but it's happening within the same mineral group.

534 uncover correlations that could inform predictive models in geometallurgy. This step not only
 535 serves to validate the effectiveness of our autoencoder but also tests its applicability as a predic-
 536 tive tool in broader textural analysis and modelling scenarios. Applying the trained model to
 537 the unseen images, we analyse how accurately the model can predict the reconstructed images
 538 compared to the initial training set and assess its adaptability. As soon as we were convinced
 539 by the reconstruction results, we may claim that the feature vectors, which are considered to
 540 be the dense representations of a corresponding rock particle digital images, can bear some im-
 541 portant information about rock textures. Looking forward, the methodology could further be
 542 refined to include quantitative assessments such as pixel-by-pixel comparisons or more sophisti-
 543 cated shape analysis techniques to further validate the accuracy of the texture reconstructions.
 544 Such enhancements would be critical for transitioning from qualitative to quantitative validation
 545 frameworks, providing a more robust basis for the evaluation of textural reconstructions.

546 Finally, we first addressed the dimensionality reduction of the high-dimensional feature vec-
 547 tors extracted from the bottleneck layer of our convolutional autoencoder. Using Principal
 548 Component Analysis (PCA), we aimed to simplify the complexity inherent in the data, reducing
 549 the number of dimensions to a subset that captures the most significant variance within the
 550 feature vectors. Then, we cluster the reduced feature vectors in order to find the patterns and
 551 correlate them to the production metrics. We applied PCA to the feature vectors, initially with-
 552 out specifying the number of components, to evaluate the cumulative variance explained by each
 553 subsequent component (Figure 11). This analysis was crucial to determine the optimal number

554 of principal components required to capture the core information of the dataset effectively. The
555 cumulative variance plot indicated that approximately 200 components were sufficient to explain
556 90% of the total variance. This substantial reduction from the original dimensions allowed us
557 to focus on the most informative features while eliminating redundancy and noise.

Figure 11: An example of cumulative explained variance plot for one of the feature vectors.

558 With the dimensionality reduced to 200 principal components, we proceeded with clustering
559 the compressed feature vectors to uncover inherent groupings and patterns. We employed two
560 distinct clustering approaches:

- 561 • **Self-Organizing Maps (SOMs):** This method was utilised to project the high-dimensional
562 data onto a two-dimensional grid, preserving the topological properties of the input space.
563 This allowed us to visually interpret the clustering results and understand the spatial
564 distribution of data points.
- 565 • **K-means Clustering:** We applied K-means clustering to categorise the feature vectors
566 into 25 distinct clusters, a number derived from preliminary experiments that suggested it
567 as an optimal balance for our dataset. This method helped identify discrete groups within
568 the data, facilitating a more structured analysis of texture patterns.

569 In our study, we employed two distinct clustering methods to analyse the feature vectors: k-
570 means clustering and Self-Organizing Maps (SOM). The rationale behind choosing these methods
571 was to leverage their unique approaches to clustering, thus capturing a comprehensive range

572 of potential clustering outcomes. This diversity in methods also allowed us to validate the
573 robustness of our clustering results across different algorithmic paradigms.

574 We utilised k-means clustering with 25 clusters. The choice of 25 clusters was not arbitrary;
575 it was determined through an iterative process of optimisation using silhouette scores. Silhouette
576 scores provide a measure of how similar an object is to its own cluster compared to other clusters.
577 A higher silhouette score indicates that the object is well-matched to its own cluster and poorly
578 matched to neighbouring clusters. By iterating over different cluster numbers and calculating
579 their silhouette scores, we identified 25 as the optimal number of clusters, balancing complexity
580 and interpretability.

581 In addition to k-means, we employed SOM for clustering, choosing 226 clusters. SOM, a
582 type of unsupervised neural network, provides a powerful tool for visualising high-dimensional
583 data by projecting it onto a lower-dimensional grid while preserving topological relationships.
584 The number of clusters (nodes) in the SOM was estimated based on the size of the dataset, with
585 76101 feature vectors. We aimed to cover the entire range of data effectively, ensuring that each
586 cluster represented a unique aspect of the data’s distribution.

587 The number of SOM clusters was derived by calculating the optimal map size, ensuring
588 sufficient granularity to capture the diverse patterns in the feature vectors. Unlike k-means, SOM
589 clusters are organised in a grid, which provides a visual representation of the data’s structure
590 and helps in understanding the relationships between clusters.

591 By employing both k-means and SOM, we ensured a thorough exploration of the clustering
592 landscape. These methods vary significantly in their approach: k-means minimises intra-cluster
593 variance, while SOM maintains the topological properties of the data. This dual approach
594 allowed us to cross-validate the clustering results and ensure their robustness and reliability.

595 The independence of cluster numbers between k-means and SOM reflects their different
596 clustering logics. K-means clusters were directly influenced by the silhouette score optimisa-
597 tion, while SOM clusters were based on the grid size needed to represent the feature vectors
598 adequately. This difference underscores the complementarity of the two methods in providing a
599 holistic understanding of the data.

600 The clustering results were visualised using bar plots (Figure 12 and 13), which depicted
601 the distribution of images across the determined clusters. This not only provided a clear visual
602 representation of the dominant groupings within the dataset but also highlighted the network’s
603 ability to generalise and categorise complex textural patterns effectively.

Figure 12: SOM clusters. Each colour represents a particular cluster. Totally 226 clusters.

Figure 13: k-Means clusters. Each colour represents a particular cluster. Totally 25 clusters.

604 These steps in our methodology underscored the robustness of the convolutional autoencoder
605 in handling and interpreting the textural complexity of MLA images. By linking the compressed
606 representations from the autoencoder with geological characteristics and production metrics, we
607 are currently being able to draw meaningful insights that have potential applications in enhanc-
608 ing the accuracy and efficiency of texture analysis in geosciences, particularly in geometallurgy.
609 The ultimate test of OdysseyNet’s utility came from the analysis of feature vectors extracted
610 from the reconstructed images. By transforming these vectors into a bar plot representation of
611 clusters, we were able to identify textural anomalies and correlate these findings with the pro-
612 duction metrics of corresponding rock samples. This approach underscored the potential of our
613 methodology to offer meaningful insights into the textural characteristics of geological samples,
614 which are pivotal for predicting their processing behaviour. Details of potential funding and
615 further developments will be discussed in subsequent publications.

616 **4 Conclusion and Future Work**

617 The OdysseyNet framework successfully demonstrated that convolutional autoencoders could
618 identify and learn complex textural patterns in MLA images used in geometallurgy. By employ-
619 ing a structured approach to build and refine the network architecture, the study managed to
620 capture essential texture features without detailed reconstruction, focusing instead on pattern
621 recognition and its implications for production metrics. The extracted feature vectors, reduced
622 via PCA and clustered, formed a basis for analysing textural patterns across different rock sam-
623 ples. This research paves the way for future studies to enhance unsupervised learning models in
624 industrial applications, particularly in sectors where understanding material properties is crucial
625 and current methods are invasive or impractical. Further work will aim to refine these techniques
626 and explore their predictive capabilities in correlation with actual production outcomes, with
627 results to be detailed in subsequent publications.

628 **5 Data and Code Availability**

629 The datasets used in this study are proprietary to BHP and were made available solely for re-
630 search and demonstration purposes; they will not be published. The author does not claim any
631 ownership of the datasets. The neural network OdysseyNet is available at [https://github.com/Sasha-](https://github.com/Sasha-Roslyn/Telemetis)
632 [Roslyn/Telemetis](https://github.com/Sasha-Roslyn/Telemetis). The trained network with current weights is distributed under a non-commercial

633 licence (CC BY-NC 4.0). The source code and intellectual property related to further indepen-
634 dent development remain with the author (Alexandra Roslin).

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639 **Literature**

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